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Current strategy of personnel policy formation in public administration

Serhiy Tarasov¹, Kyrylo Pasynchuk¹, Iuliia Panimash, and Yuriy Horbachenko¹

¹ Cherkasy Institute of Fire Safety named after Chernobyl Heroes of National University of Civil Defense of Ukraine

Abstract. The article deals with the peculiarities of the current strategy of personnel policy formation in public administration, defines the innovation concept, the components of the innovation process in the public administration system. The basic indicators of the current innovative concept of personnel policy formation in the market economy conditions are highlighted, stemming from the following ideas: flexibility and adaptability of human resource development strategy, putting together people and their property and power, which ensures every person's freedom for occupation, active participation in personnel policy decision and its further implementation at the state, region and enterprise levels, flexibility and novel technologies of HR management activities.

1 Introduction

In today's global economy, synergies can be traced between management culture and policy at different hierarchical levels. The focus on cooperation and teamwork to overcome market inertia and achieving a breakthrough in economic and social activities has become so crucial that they speak about the organizational revolution, about "the new economy", the innovative culture of public administration. The 15-year experience of Ukraine has proved that the winner is not the one who has more resources, but the one who acts faster and with more creativity. Hence, the new requirements for the enterprise have led to the formation of a new culture of relationships, administration, interaction, and process structuring [1, p. 112].

The culture concept has two main meanings. Firstly, it characterizes civilization, creation of mind which is implemented in literature and art; secondly, it is a mindset reflecting typical thoughts, behavior and deeds of people, their problem-solving techniques.

Each society exists in its own local and, simultaneously, the global environment defining commanding ideas of the century, technologies, institutes, traditions. The public administration system is developed within the framework of cooperation of national culture, institutes, and policy with the local and global environment. Firstly, the culture is formed which is later, integrally with other factors, helps develop the economic system. There is also a feedback effect, such as globalization changes national and business culture facilitating convergence in one way or another [2].

2 Presenting main material

In recent years, the problem of business market culture cultivation in Ukraine has transformed into the necessity of mainly innovative: culture at the state, region, corporation

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and individual levels. To our mind, the innovation concept is defined too narrow in the Great Economic Dictionary [3, p. 10] as:

- 1) investment into the economy, which provides a change in processes and technology;
- 2) a new technique, technology, which resulted from scientific and technological progress.

The Popular Economic Encyclopedia [4] gives a deeper consideration to the concept: innovations are novelties, the ultimate outcome of innovative activity, related to investments into the economy which ensure the change of generations in processes and technology. The innovative activity promotes the transformation of the idea embedded in the scientific researches and developments into a new or advanced product applied to the market; into a new or advanced technological process applied in practice, or a new approach to social services. There are five types of innovations in the public administration system: the introduction of a new product, introduction of a new method of production, creation of a new market, development of a new source of supply of raw materials and semi-finished products, reorganization of the management structure.

Considering this category under the present conditions, taking into account the conditions of development of socio-economic systems, it is possible to speak about the innovations in the system of formation and development of the personnel policy of the state, region, enterprise as a cornerstone of successful economic development. The practice of market conditions forces each system to introduce various innovations, taking into account changes occurring in the external environment. The rapidly improving state, region, and enterprise must constantly make changes to the management system, social and economic environment to be well-positioned to retaining their competitive advantages.

As a result of changes in the environment, both new needs and new knowledge emerge, the means to meet those needs [5]. In our opinion, new knowledge, methods, technologies of development of any system are also novations.

Regional innovative culture and politics are largely dependent on the state policy, but the real implementation of this policy takes place at the regional and enterprise levels. It allows adapting and organically integrating this policy into the possibilities and needs of territorial policy and culture.

Nowadays, there is no doubt that only an innovative system can be competitive and effectively built up in a market environment. Therefore, the socioeconomic policy should primarily be focused on creating an innovative environment nationwide.

The experience of the world economic development shows that deep, effective transformations of the economy are possible only with the active use of the modern achievements of scientific and technological progress and constant improvement of the system of public administration in Ukraine.

The development prospect of innovative activity in the economy of Ukraine is interconnected, firstly, with the Strategy for Sustainable Development "Ukraine-2020" [6].

This document sets two major interdependent public policy directions in the sphere:

- developing national innovation system;
- keeping and developing of the human capacity of the scientific and technological corporation of the state.

Scientific and technological developments and inventions are additional new knowledge for practical application, and scientific innovations are the implementation of new ideas and knowledge, discoveries, inventions for their realization to satisfy specific consumer or market demands. Indispensable properties of innovations are their scientific and technological novelty. Innovative marketability is a potential property that requires some

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effort. Therefore, "innovation - the result" must be considered in its indispensable link with the innovation process.

Three values are equally inherent in innovation: scientific and technical novelty, demand, and implementation. However, the innovation effectiveness is determined by the balance or merger of interests of the developing system (innovation process), which can be represented as a simulation model.

According to this model, the innovation process effectiveness (innovation activity effectiveness) is defined not only by the internal capabilities of the organization, that is, the qualitative characteristics of the resources of the given enterprise but also by the external components of the process, such as demand for novation and marketing activities. This model is characteristic of the first variant of innovation activity, where the innovation "seeks" its application. According to this model, a novation is the final stage of innovation, because the process of innovation activity began with market research and demand generation, and only then can this "need" be realized in the form of the novation in real production.

In our view, under market conditions, the first and second options can be effective if the components of the innovation process are balanced.

The economic mechanism of public administration of innovation activity should also comprise marketing costs, because under market conditions they, to a great extent, determine the performance efficiency of any system.

Therefore, novations for any socio-economic system, including personnel policy-making systems, are implemented and effective if they adhere to these parameters. In such a case, in the market economy conditions, only a system that is capable of innovative change can survive and develop.

Having regard to the above, it can be concluded that the innovative economy is the ability of the socio-economic system to invest resource capital into the development of new technologies, techniques, methods, and ideas of effective interaction of entities and facilities of economic, social and scientific activities. For the state, region, and enterprise, skillful support for innovation activity is a certain guarantee for the effective promotion of future novations and sustainable economic growth.

Innovations in the system of formation and development of public administration of personnel policy of socio-economic systems are new methods, technologies, principles and innovative structures of the process of development and use of human resources.

The difficulty of the construction of a system of public administration of innovations during the formation and implementation of the state personnel policy lies in the fact that the region has a very complex organizational structure and manages numerous processes, and even the number of personnel structures is characterized by a great polyvariety. Therefore, the organizational system of public administration of innovations in the system of formation of personnel policy of the state and the region should be aimed at maximizing its potential and mechanisms of public administration of current activity.

Therefore, the modern innovativeness of the concept of personnel policy formation in the market economy conditions is in the following provisions:

- flexibility and adaptability of the strategy of human resources development formation;
- putting together people and their property and power, which ensures every person's freedom for occupation;
- recognition of the right of many management entities to address the issue of reproduction of labor-power;

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- active participation in the choice of personnel policy and its implementation at the state, regional and enterprise level;
- flexible mechanisms and innovative technologies of HR management activities;
- constant reproduction of innovative technologies of personnel policy formation;
- social responsibility in the formation, development, and use of human resources of socio-economic systems;
- constant innovation of technologies, methods, and approaches in the formation of personnel policy.

National and regional innovation policy is focused on solving territorial problems, which include the effective use of available logistics, raw materials, and labor potentials, meeting the needs of the domestic market. This innovation policy is implemented through the programs of improving the competitive potential of top-priority industries by involving private institutional investors to the implementation of innovations; formation of the mode of innovative activity economic encouragement.

National and regional innovation policies are a constituent of the economic policy of regional authorities responsible for the creation of favorable conditions for commercial, manufacturing, agroindustrial, construction and industrial science, and scientific and production integration of all institutional business patterns.

The innovation policy of various authorities which is an important factor in stabilization, recovery and economic growth, supposes a robust relationship between the entities of commercial relations. These entities include:

- scientific-research and development organs;
- educational institutions;
- production and agricultural enterprises;
- building industry enterprises and construction and installation contractors;
- credit institutions, insurance companies;
- commercial enterprises and supply-sale cooperative enterprises;
- regional infrastructure;
- authorities at all levels.

The organization of these entities determines the effectiveness of innovation culture and innovation activity. But, under the legislation enacted in Ukraine, which empowered the entities to exercise local self-government, local authorities are entitled to create financial and credit organizations and institutions, target budget funds, to establish under the current Ukrainian legislation local taxes and other payments, to introduce state tax exemptions coming to the local budget, to participate with their funds in the activities of enterprises and organizations. The increase in budget revenues is directly dependent on the growth of the income of taxpayers who pay taxes to the regional budget, that is, on the competitiveness of the production facilities located on the territory.

As far as the application of innovations provides a monopoly high entrepreneurial income, all authorities are interested in enhancing the innovation potential of any socio-economic system and intensifying its innovation activity.

The state and regional systems of financial support of innovative activity are formed by sources of formation of financial resources, the mechanism of accumulation of funds

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coming from these sources, the mechanisms of invested funds control and recovery. The sources of financial resources are:

1. State non-budgetary funds allocations for the implementation of regional and state-scale projects, as well as funds available for the region, from the allotments of enterprises and organizations to the state non-budgetary funds related to R&D and investments in production modernization and technological restoration (in the amount of 5-10%)
2. Regional pension funds allocations to support small innovative ventures (in the amount of 2-5 %).
3. Grants and transfers from the state budget for the implementation of state programs and innovative projects, contracted by state authorities.
4. Targeted funds from the state and local budgets.
5. Allocations of the income of economic entities by the implementation of innovative projects and programs, as well as the revenues of institutes of market infrastructure created with the assistance or by way of promotion of regional authorities.
6. Income from fund exchange operation with innovators' shares, from emission and conversion of state and regional securities, mobilizing for investment programs.
7. Contributions by enterprises and private persons aimed at economic innovation funding.
8. Income from the implementation of regional programs and projects.
9. Foreign investments into innovation activity.

Committees or other structural units that determine and facilitate the implementation of innovative policies of socio-economic systems should work effectively in the management of state structures, in municipal and regional administrations. The documented provisions of this policy should include a set of major projects and activities, the implementation of which is aimed at the development of competitive industries and technologies, the use of local natural resources, production and labor potential, the creation of product and technological innovations, etc.

The processes of formation and development of socio-economic and human resources are successful only when they are based on the results of forecasting of the condition and dynamics of the environment, identifying external and internal factors and conditions that can significantly affect the pace of economic development. Therefore, nowadays, the innovative capabilities of any system determined by the degree of innovation of specific manufacturers are of particular importance. The main characteristics that reflect the innovative capabilities of socio-economic systems are the use of intellectual property subject matter, the results of the introduction and implementation of inventions and innovation proposals, the level of innovation activity, sources of funding for technological, managerial and social innovations.

3 Conclusions from the conducted research

State innovation management in the market economy conditions in Ukraine is a completely new and unexplored layer in science and practice. It should take into account the specific cultural, historical and geographical features of the territory.

In our view, the concept of innovation management in the system of personnel policy public administration is rooted in the following principles: the need for constant innovative development of the mechanism of personnel policy formation, technological advancement, flexibility and adaptability of personnel policy under market transformations, the need to develop a strategy for the personnel policy formation, innovation activity feasibility, social

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responsibility, creation of uniform principles of strategic management of the process of personnel policy formation, personnel policy integration at different levels of government, coordination of institutional structures activities.

A prerequisite to the innovation culture formation is an elaboration of state and regional innovation support programs.

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